

OpenWebSearch.eu

“Piloting a Cooperative Open Web Search Infrastructure to Support Europe’s Digital Sovereignty”

Deliverable D2.3 Semantic Enrichment Algorithms and Models

Version 1.0

Open Web Search

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Preliminaries

i. Project Info

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ii. Project Partners

Acronym	Partner
UNI PASSAU	University of Passau
BADW-LRZ	Leibniz Supercomputing Centre of the Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities
RU	Radboud University
WEBIS	Leipzig University
TUGraz	Graz University of Technology
DLR	German Aerospace Center
CERN	CERN
IT4I@VSB	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar (Associated Partner)
OSF	Open Search Foundation e.V.
A1	A1 Slovenia
SUMA-EV	Suma e.V. (Associated Partner)
CSC	CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy
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iv. Deliverable Summary

This document reviews the status of Deliverable D2.3 "Semantic Enrichment Algorithms and Models" of the OpenWebSearch.eu project, which is supported by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme under grant agreement GA 101070014. The deliverable is reviewed in comparison to the objectives planned in the proposal, and with respect to how it integrates with other components of the project. The document also outlines the anticipated plans for further development until the end of the project.

¹ Michael Granitzer, Stefan Voigt, Noor Afshan Fathima, Martin Golasowski, Christian Guetl, Tobias Hecking, Gijs Hendriksen, Djoerd Hiemstra, Jan Martinovič, Jelena Mitrovič, Izidor Mlakar, Stavros Moiras, Alexander Nussbaumer, Per Öster, Martin Potthast, Marjana Senčar Srdič, Sharikadze Megi, Kateřina Slaninová, Benno Stein, Arjen P. de Vries, Vít Vondrák, Andreas Wagner, Saber Zerhoudi (2023). [Impact and development of an Open Web Index for open web search](#). In Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology.

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vii. Executive Summary

We report on the current state of research and development to enable the semantic enrichment of the Open Web Index (OWI) with relevant information for users and third parties. This information makes it possible to filter the index for specific subsets of documents to create specialized indexes for specific search applications, to augment retrieval models for ranking documents, and to display web documents in search results pages with additional information.

Our main contributions are the following:

1. Content analysis by web page classification: Implementation of modules for classifying entire web pages with respect to indexing-relevant criteria. This includes, among other things, the genre classification of a web page as well as the subsequent creation and maintenance of application-specific indexes (“collection indexes”).
2. Content analysis of web page segments: Ongoing research into extracting information and metadata from specific parts of a web page. Examples include identifying geographic information, detecting AI-generated content, and analyzing arguments on a web page.
3. Computational ethics: Ongoing research on the detection of LLM-generated content, the detection and blocking of LLM-generated advertising in retrieval-augmented generation (RAG), and the assignment of trigger warnings to potentially disturbing web documents.
4. Embeddings and language models: Ongoing research to create embeddings for web documents to enable the creation of RAG-based search systems, especially in a multilingual context.

1. Introduction

The OpenWebSearch.eu (OWS.eu) project is focused on creating an open-access index, the OpenWebIndex (OWI). The OWI consists of two main components: index files and metadata files. The index files enable search applications to retrieve documents that are relevant to a particular search query. The metadata files complement the index files by providing additional information about each document in the index. Examples include the genre of a web page or the geographical locations mentioned on it.

The main use cases for the metadata are threefold: First, the retrieval of subsets of the OWI by providers of specific search applications to create tailored indexes, for example, for French news. Second, the display of contextual information to end users on search engine results pages (SERPs), for example, whether a document contains potentially distressing content, such as discussions of abuse or depression. This enables users to make informed decisions about whether they want to visit a particular web page and lays the foundation for the information nutrition label. Third, the metadata can also be integrated into search application-specific retrieval models to improve the ranking of certain types of documents.

The tasks aimed at generating different types of metadata can be collectively referred to as semantic enrichment. In this report, we present the current state of our activities in the Tasks 2.2 “Content Analysis”, 2.3 “Computational Ethics”, 2.5 “Geocoding and Geotagging” and 2.7 “Embeddings and Language Models for Multilingual RAG-based Systems”².

In light of the project's reorientation with a stronger focus on retrieval augmented generation (RAG) and generative AI in general as a result of the mid-term review, many of the tasks in Work Package 2 have been revised accordingly. In particular, we plan to extend the more traditional content analysis methods in Task 2.2 with the development of classification methods for recognizing content generated by large language models (LLMs). Since it has become easy to generate large amounts of text with both public and proprietary services, the prevalence of LLM-generated content on the web is likely to increase in the future. Therefore, methods that can distinguish LLM-generated content from human-written content will likely be valuable for both search applications and data collection for natural language processing (NLP) tasks. With our research in Task 2.2, we want to help advance the development of such methods. In addition, we are investigating the usefulness of LLMs in argument search as an exemplary search application. To provide an overview of a particular discourse, a large number of arguments must be compiled, summarized, and presented concisely. This requires both a semantic understanding of the arguments and the creation of summary statements that capture their gist. LLMs prove useful for both of these tasks.

In Task 2.3, we aim to make greater use of LLMs in the context of computational ethics. The first application is in LLM-based trigger warning assignment. While the presence of some types of distressing content can be identified at the lexical level alone, other content requires detection at the semantic level. LLMs are well suited for this task. Besides the more harmful types of content, we are also interested in detecting content that may merely be annoying for web users but not harmful. Furthermore, given the importance of advertising as a business model on the Internet in general and in search applications in particular, it is conceivable that providers of LLMs and RAG systems choose this business model to cover the significant costs associated with operating these systems.

² Note that the Task 2.7 has been adapted compared to the original project plan to address recent advancements in large language models for search.

Advertising directly integrated into LLMs' responses would not be recognizable by conventional ad blockers. To enable users to block this type of advertising, we are researching the detection of advertising at the semantic level using LLMs and smaller transformers such as Sentence-BERT.

Task 2.5 is concerned with linking web pages to geographical locations. Besides extracting this information from microformats provided by the owners of a web page, this is also possible by identifying geographical entities in the text of a web page. While LLMs are able to accomplish this task and extract locations from text, they are not as efficient as smaller models. To leverage both the high effectiveness of LLMs and the efficiency of smaller models, we plan to use LLMs for data annotation. This allows us to create customized datasets from the web pages already crawled during the project, which in turn can be used to train smaller models for the specific task of identifying locations in web data.

To improve the quality of LLM-generated content, retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) provides external knowledge to LLMs at the time of inference. Many variants of RAG systems depend on access to up-to-date web data in the form of semantic embeddings. We seek to support the research and development of RAG systems by providing embeddings as representations of web documents in the OWI. To make this happen, we are working on chunking methods to divide web documents into manageable parts and evaluate different embedding models for their suitability for RAG systems. Furthermore, we are exploring a framework for integrating personal information into agent-based RAG systems to increase the relevance of the generated content for an individual user.

Additional research is needed to refocus the tasks as described above. Therefore, the tasks have been extended beyond their original time frames set in the proposal. In the following chapters, we present the research and development activities already carried out for the respective tasks and outline our future plans. In Chapter 2, the activities in Task 2.2 “Content Analysis” are discussed with regard to the classification of full web pages and the analysis of segments of a page. The current state of the geoparsing functions developed in Task 2.5 “Geocoding and Geotagging” is also presented. Chapter 3 describes our research in Task 2.3 “Computational Ethics”, in particular in the area of ad detection and automatic trigger warning assignment. The research conducted in Task 2.7 “Embeddings and Language Models for Multilingual RAG-based Systems” is presented in Chapter 4. Chapter 5 summarizes the results obtained so far.

2. Content Analysis

During the first half of the OpenWebSearch.EU project, we developed Resilipipe, a framework to process and analyze large web crawls using HPC cluster infrastructure. Resilipipe uses our open-source web archive processing library Resiliparse to parse WARC files and extract metadata. As outlined in Deliverable 2.1 “The OpenWebSearch WARC Parsing & Content Analysis Library”, the extraction results include information from the WARC and HTTP headers, Microdata, and JSON Linked Data, the language of the web document, and the document’s plain text.

Resilipipe is designed to be extended in a modular fashion to expand the range of metadata that can be extracted from web crawls. Both project partners as well as third parties can therefore develop their own content analysis modules using a standardized interface that we provide as part of our Resilipipe repository.³ The following sections present modules that are either already part of Resilipipe or the subject of active research.

2.1 Web Page Classification

Downstream applications using the Open Web Index (OWI) might only be interested in a subset of web pages relevant to their use case. In order to facilitate the selection of relevant subsets, a group of Resilipipe modules is concerned with classifying web pages with respect to different criteria. One module, called Curlielabels, was already briefly mentioned in Deliverable 2.1: This module assigns each web page a genre label derived from the categorization developed by the community of Curlie.org⁴ and a curated dataset of domain labels.⁵ Based on these labels, the OWI can be reduced to any desired combination of categories such as “Arts”, “Education”, or “Computers”.

In the following subsections, we present two additional modules that classify web pages to facilitate the selection of specific types of documents from the OWI.

2.1.1 Web Page Genre Classification

We approach the classification of a web page into genres from two angles. The aforementioned module Curlielabels assigns web pages a genre label based on their domain. In addition to that, we are developing a module that classifies a web page based on its content.

Specifically, the module will use the web page’s plain text to estimate the probability for a set of eight classes (see Table 1). The set of genres as well as a corresponding training corpus of web pages is based on previous research in the Webis Group.⁶

In March 2024, we co-organized a hackathon at the Technical University in Dresden for the Workshop on Open Search.⁷ One group developed a genre classifier that we will build upon. Using a multilayer perceptron, their classifier achieved a test accuracy of 79.10%.

Genre
Article
Discussion
Download
Help
Link Collection
Portrait (Non-Private)
Portrait (Private)
Shop

Table 1: Content Genres

³ Refer to <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/preprocessing-pipeline> for the repository.

⁴ Refer to <https://curlie.org/docs/en/about.html> for more information.

⁵ Lugeon, Sylvain; Piccardi, Tiziano (2022). [Curlie Dataset - Language-agnostic Website Embedding and Classification](#).

⁶ Sven Meyer zu Eissen & Benno Stein [2004](#), [2006](#), [2008](#), [2010](#).

⁷ Refer to <https://opensearchfoundation.org/wows2024> for more information.

2.1.2 Collection Indices

To enable downstream applications to select subsets of the OWI according to their specific requirements, we want to offer predefined subsets that are likely relevant to many applications. We call these subsets “collection indices.” The collection indices are created directly in our preprocessing and indexing pipeline by identifying web pages that, according to predefined criteria, are part of a collection index.

```
indices:
- name: curlie_full
  metadata:
    storage: system
    description: "The index contains the full curlie dataset for all languages.
    A page is in the dataset, if the domain is contained in curlie."
  filters:
    ows_curlielabel*: .*
    curlielabels_en*: */en/*
```

Figure 1: Example Structure for a Collection Index YAML-file

A new collection index can be added to the pipeline by choosing one or multiple columns of the schema⁸ of the parquet files of the index and defining criteria that the content of these columns should fulfill. This collection index definition is done using YAML-files with a predefined structure (see Figure 1). The “filters”-mapping defines the criteria a web page has to fulfill to be assigned to the respective collection index. Each key in the mapping is a column in the aforementioned schema and the corresponding value defines a regular expression or a string to be matched with the content of that column. In the example of Figure 1, a web page is assigned to the collection index “curlie_full” if its “ows_curlielabel”-column is not empty or if the column “curlielabels_en” contains the pattern “/en/”.

The YAML-files are parsed by the collection indices module to apply the filtering definitions to the web pages in each daily crawl. This setup allows for both a flexible definition collection indices as well as easy addition of new indices. The first two collection indices contain (1) all web pages with a Curlie label, and (2) all web pages that are likely to contain legal information based on patterns in the URL such as “imprint”, “legal” or “terms”.

⁸ Refer to the repository for the schema: <https://opencode.it4i.eu/openwebsearcheu-public/preprocessing-pipeline>.

2.2 Web Page Segment Analysis

Besides classifying full web pages with respect to certain criteria, some search applications also require the extraction of information from a web page, or the classification of segments from a web page with respect to certain criteria. Resiliparse hence also offers the capability to first parse a web page and then analyze only segments of it.

2.2.1 Geocoding and Geotagging

The goal of the Geocoding and Geotagging approach is to associate web content with accurate geographic locations. Web search applications mostly rely on locations explicitly provided by content providers or user-reported locations to link web resources to geographic entities, which leaves the majority of web content without location information. Hence, extracting geographic information from unstructured web content at scale can add significant value for building a geo-enriched search index. This type of index can, in turn, make certain applications easier to develop and maintain. Examples include geographical information retrieval, improved situational awareness for crisis management, localized searches of real estate, attractions, products, and environmental studies.

Through extensive testing of various existing geoparsers, we have determined that no readily available solution sufficiently handles the diverse structure and language of web data while also simultaneously being efficient enough to process data at the scale of the web. Existing solutions we have tested include the Edinburgh Geoparser, CLAVIN, Mordecai, and Camcoder. While each of them performs well for their specific use cases, none are viable for web-scale geoparsing. Table 2 shows our findings from comparing several geoparsers on the basis of critical metrics such as runtime, location coverage, multilingual data support, integration effort etc. Green indicates positive aspects whereas red indicates negative and yellow indicates undetermined.

Models Metrics	CamCoder	CLAVIN	Mordecai	Edinburgh Geoparser	Geoparsepy	GENRE	Topocluster	LLM	NER +Gazetteer
Time Consumption	High	Low	High	High			Very High	High	Low
Multilingual	Yes*	No	No	Yes*	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
External Gazetteer	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		No	Yes
Coordinates	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No			Yes	Yes
Location Coverage		High	High	High	High			High	High
External Dependencies	None	Maven, Java	Docker	API	Postgre			Hardware*	None
Integration Effort	High	Low	High	High	High	High			Low

Table 2: Comparison of Geoparsers

We have identified a critical trade-off between accuracy and speed when geoparsing at web-scale. Geoparsing involves a two-step process: first, identifying locations within the text, and second, mapping these locations to geographic coordinates. We have mirrored this approach by utilizing Named Entity Recognition (NER) for location identification and subsequently employing a location

gazetteer (a collection of locations and associated coordinates) to map these locations to coordinates. This process includes a disambiguation step to determine the correct coordinates when multiple geographic entities share the same name. Compared to other geoparsing solutions, this approach is more time-efficient and is able to handle multilingual web data.

Currently, we are optimizing these steps separately to ensure they integrate effectively into the Resilipipe framework. We have tested several NER models, including Flair, SpaCy, and StanfordNER. While Flair offers better accuracy, but its runtime costs exceed those of SpaCy by a large margin, especially for longer texts. SpaCy includes a multilingual model that has acceptable accuracy while maintaining a good balance in terms of runtime. We are exploring fine-tuning this model to increase accuracy further. At the same time, we are testing whether fine-tuned and quantized BERT models can be used for scalable location recognition.

For geocoding, we use a local copy of GeoNames data as a gazetteer. We are combining this dataset with OpenStreetMaps to increase geographic coverage and are writing our own disambiguation algorithms for conflicting locations. Once these individual parts are optimized and combined, we will have a geoparser that can successfully extract and map locations to coordinates from text of any structure and support multilingual data.

Furthermore, our investigation into the application of Large Language Models (LLMs) for geoparsing has shown that, while direct geoparsing with LLMs is feasible, it is a time-consuming process. Instead, we use LLMs to annotate data, which can then be utilized to train smaller models for location detection and to validate our geoparsing solutions.

In addition to extracting geographic information from text, we make use of the geographic data provided by webpage owners in microformats associated with the web pages. We extract these structured addresses directly from the microformats—a task that is essentially a pattern-matching operation. This way of extracting geographic entities is highly efficient and has been integrated into Resilipipe.

In future plans for this task, alongside developing a feasible geoparser for web content, we will also explore the context of locations by relating them to other content on web pages.

2.2.2 Identification of AI-Generated Content

With Generative Artificial Intelligence, it has become much easier to mass-produce content on the web. This poses a challenge for web users and search engines in finding original content and judging its authenticity and veracity. In a study we conducted on the use of affiliate marketing on the web and its impact on search engines,⁹ we found that, in the product review web genre, much of the existing content is heavily optimized for search engines and of questionable quality. Affiliate marketing is an easy and sometimes “lazy” way to monetize a web presence. Users are referred to the seller of a product via a special link which earns the referrer a commission on product views or sales. Affiliate marketing requires content as a vehicle to be indexed and found by search engines, but since users are expected to dwell only long enough on a page to click a link, it does not necessarily require strict quality criteria for it. This makes affiliate marketing well-suited for

⁹ Janek Bevendorff, Matti Wiegmann, Martin Potthast, & Benno Stein (2024). [Is Google Getting Worse? A Longitudinal Investigation of SEO Spam in Search Engines](#). In *Advances in Information Retrieval*. 46th European Conference on IR Research (ECIR 2024).

deployment at scale with mass-produced and of course potentially AI-generated content. With more than 90 reports, the study was well received in the media¹⁰ speaking to the timeliness of the issue.

As a starting point to assess and tackle the problem of AI-generated content as a suspected driver behind or accelerator of said low-quality content, we organized a scientific challenge on AI detection in the form of a Shared Task at the CLEF conference 2024.¹¹ In preparation, we re-implemented several state-of-the-art detection systems as baselines and collected and generated comprehensive training and test datasets of real and fake news articles using a variety of state-of-the-art large language models, including GPT-4, GPT-3.5, Gemini Pro, PaLM2, Llama2, Mistral, and others. The task received 95 registrations of which 30 participants submitted systems. All submitted systems were evaluated with regard to their overall effectiveness, but also their resilience towards unexpected out-of-domain data by creating dataset variants with several applied text obfuscations. On the regular test dataset, many systems achieved a near-perfect detection rate. This means that the current generation of LLMs is still very detectable, at the very least if the texts are sufficiently long and have not been edited to hide their AI authorship. On the resilience-focused test dataset, on the other hand, many of the approaches failed entirely. Yet several systems were still successful although with significantly lower scores (the best systems performed approximately 5–10% worse).

As a next step, we plan to adapt the best-performing approaches, integrate them into the content analysis pipeline, and run experiments at larger scales to conduct prevalence studies on crawled web content.

2.2.3 Argument Analysis / Detection

Argument search engines like args.me,¹² as an example of vertical search engines in our project, are designed to provide users a contrastive view of pro and contra arguments on a controversial topic. They give an overview of important aspects that are discussed in a debate and offer additional resources as a starting point for users to explore the topic in more detail.

One challenge in creating such argument search engines is the abundance of arguments that can be retrieved from the web. These arguments are often lengthy and, while formulated differently, inherently redundant. This requires a strategy for grouping and summarizing arguments for their meaningful presentation. In the context of Task 2.2, we therefore work on the generation of so-called key points—high-level statements serving as a kind of summary of multiple arguments.¹³ They are succinctly written and have a specific stance. One example is the key point “*School uniforms are expensive*” with stance pro for the topic “*We should abandon the use of school uniforms*”.

¹⁰ Media Coverage: [Is Google Getting Worse? - Media Coverage](#) (online).

¹¹ PAN Shared Task: <https://pan.webis.de/clef24/pan24-web/generated-content-analysis.html>;

Overview Paper: Janek Bevendorff, Matti Wiegmann, Jussi Karlgren, Luise Durlich, Evangelia Gogoulou, Aarne Talman, Efstathios Stamatatos, Martin Potthast, & Benno Stein (2024). [Overview of the “Voight-Kampff” Generative AI Authorship Verification Task at PAN and ELOQUENT 2024](#). In Working Notes of CLEF 2024 – Conference and Labs of the Evaluation Forum.

¹² Paper: Wachsmuth, H., Potthast, M., Al-Khatib, K., Ajour, Y., Puschmann, J., Qu, J., Dorsch, J., Morari, V., Bevendorff, J., & Stein, B. (2017). [Building an Argument Search Engine for the Web](#). In Proceedings of the 4th Workshop on Argument Mining;

Demo: <https://www.args.me/index.html>.

¹³ Bar-Haim, R., Eden, L., Friedman, R., Kantor, Y., Lahav, D., & Slonim, N. (2020). [From Arguments to Key Points: Towards Automatic Argument Summarization](#). In Proceedings of the 58th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics;

Bar-Haim, R., Kantor, Y., Eden, L., Friedman, R., Lahav, D., & Slonim, N. (2020). [Quantitative argument summarization and beyond: Cross-domain key point analysis](#). In Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP).

The goal of our ongoing research is to create a complete key point generation pipeline. For a given (controversial) topic queried in an argument search engine, the pipeline outputs related key points with their matching arguments. We work with the dataset of the args.me search engine that contains posts extracted from different debate portals¹⁴ and thereby provides texts with a high density of arguments.

In the first step of the pipeline, we address the segmentation of debate texts into argumentative discourse units, each covering a different facet of the topic at hand. Non-argumentative text passages are filtered based on an argument quality score. The main challenge of the segmentation step is that the exact boundaries of an argumentative discourse unit are often debatable. This makes the definition of a ground truth and, as a consequence, also the evaluation of automatic approaches difficult. In addition to that, the debate texts contain implicit arguments (for example in the form of rhetorical questions) and references to previous posts. This further complicates the extraction of independent and self-contained arguments. Given these challenges, we test the suitability of LLMs for the segmentation task and propose a new evaluation approach based on soft segmentation boundaries.

In a next step, the resulting units should be clustered into groups of arguments with similar propositions. Then, a key point can be generated that represents the units in a cluster. Clustering is especially challenging in the context of argumentative segments as they already address the same meta-topic. Hence, the clustering step requires the detection of more subtle nuances of content.

The generation of key points should improve the contrastive presentation of argument results in argument search engines like args.me. The research on generating key points is expected to support the temporal analysis of arguments in Task 4.3.

¹⁴ Yamen Ajjour, Henning Wachsmuth, Johannes Kiesel, Martin Potthast, Matthias Hagen, & Benno Stein (2019). [Data Acquisition for Argument Search: The args.me corpus](#). In 42nd German Conference on Artificial Intelligence (KI 2019).

3. Computational Ethics

The previous chapter presented existing modules and ongoing research on general web content analysis. A specific area of content analysis that we are working on is computational ethics. Given the diversity of content on the Internet, some of this content may be manipulating users, or unsettling for some of them. This chapter presents our research on detecting these types of content and making the findings available to developers and users of search applications.

3.1 Advertising (by LLMs)

In the context of identifying disruptive and potentially deceptive web content in Task 2.3, we consider the scenario of LLM-generated native advertisements in the result texts of conversational search agents. Commercial conversational search engines require a financially sustainable business model and advertising is the most profitable business model in traditional search engines. It is therefore likely that advertising will continue to play an important role in search as it moves from traditional, snippet-based SERPs to conversational search agents. As further indicators, using AI for creating advertising content as well as integrating generated ads in a chat response are already on the agenda of search engine providers like Google and Bing.¹⁵

A new kind of advertising scenario that became possible with the generative capabilities of LLMs is to blend advertisements directly with the generated search result text. In a first publication, we demonstrated the feasibility of such native ads in conversational search by prompting different LLMs (YouChat and GPT-4) to promote specific brands and products in a response text generated for a search query.¹⁶ To give a concrete example, the partial sentence “*also available on Sony home theater systems*” was inserted into the text generated in response to a query about a TV show. In a user study, we showed that only about one third of the participants recognized the inserted ads in the generated texts (without being pointed to them). This demonstrates the problematic nature of this kind of advertising as it has the potential of influencing people without them realizing it. To avoid a scenario where people are unaware of the presence of advertisement in a piece of media, various trade and media regulations have been put in place that require appropriate ad disclosure. Despite these regulations, there is a clear trend towards making advertisements on search engine result pages as unobtrusive as possible. As a consequence, most users can no longer reliably recognize advertisements.¹⁷

Given that (1) LLMs offer the necessary capabilities to natively integrate advertisements into their responses and (2) a majority of users is unable to reliably recognize advertisements, we deem it important to bring up the issue of generated native ads as early as possible. Our goal is to both raise people's awareness for paid content in generated text as well as to find a way to address these ads, for example by developing new kinds of ad blockers. We already took a step in this direction by testing different models on the task of detecting native ads in generated texts.¹⁸

¹⁵ Examples include [Driving more traffic and value to publishers from the new Bing](#), [google-tests-ads-ai-overviews](#), [ai-powered-ads-google-marketing-live](#).

¹⁶ Ines Zelch, Matthias Hagen, & Martin Potthast (2024). [A User Study on the Acceptance of Native Advertising in Generative IR](#). In 9th ACM SIGIR Conference on Human Information Interaction and Retrieval (CHIIR 2024)

¹⁷ Dirk Lewandowski (2017). [Users' Understanding of Search Engine Advertisements](#). In Journal of Information Science Theory and Practice.

¹⁸ Sebastian Schmidt, Ines Zelch, Janek Bevendorff, Benno Stein, Matthias Hagen, & Martin Potthast (2024). [Detecting Generated Native Ads in Conversational Search](#). In WWW '24: Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2024.

As a first step, we created the Webis Generated Native Ads 2024 dataset,¹⁹ the first public collection of native advertisements in responses of conversational search agents. In detail, we gathered 4,800 keyword queries with a high degree of competitiveness as estimated by an SEO service.²⁰ For a given keyword, like “banking”, the service suggests associated keyword queries with estimates about (1) the number of searches per month, (2) costs per click on an ad, and (3) how competitive advertising for that query is. The selected queries were given to YouChat and Microsoft Copilot to collect their responses. To simulate an advertisement service, we prompted GPT-4 to insert ads into the responses collected in the previous step. The insertion process was guided by (1) ensuring that the advertised products and brands were associated with the queries that generated the responses and (2) defining the qualities that should be advertised about the product or brand.

For the detection step, we tried two approaches: Fine-tuned sentence transformers and LLMs in a zero-shot setting. The sentence transformers were able to achieve both high precision and recall, even on advertisements from domains they were not trained on. Without prior training, the LLMs struggled to detect the ads reliably. An analysis of the inserted ads revealed that GPT-4 has a recognizable “insertion pattern” that is likely to ease the detection in the current dataset. We plan on extending this work by expanding the corpus and exploring additional ad detection models. As part of these activities, we are offering a shared task on ad detection and insertion at the CLEF conference in 2025.²¹

Another avenue for research that goes beyond the mere detection of ads is to explore semantic ad blocking. The generative capabilities of LLMs not only make it possible to insert advertisements into texts but could also be used to rewrite text that contained an ad in a way that ensure semantic consistency. These LLM-based ad blockers could first detect an ad in a text and then remove it by replacing it with a passage that has the same meaning.

Our research on advertising in conversational search also aligns with our previously mentioned research on affiliate marketing in the sense that both are suitable monetization schemes for automatically generated content. It is reasonable to assume that generated content will become even more prevalent in the future, warranting further research on this topic.

3.2 Automated Trigger Warning Assignment

Trigger warnings are used by publishers of a piece of media to inform audiences about the presence of potentially distressing content. While originally developed as a warning about traumatic experiences in connection with sexual assault, the application of trigger warnings has extended both in terms of media they are applied to as well as the types of content being warned about.

In Task 2.3, we want to develop classifiers for the detection of content that certain audiences might want to avoid. By adding a module for trigger warning assignment to Resilipipe, we can identify web pages with potentially distressing content. In contrast to content moderation, the goal is not to remove identified content but to communicate its presence and allow developers and users of search applications to make informed decisions. As of writing this deliverable, the development of classifiers for automated trigger warning assignment is the subject of ongoing research. The following parts of this section outline the current state of that research and describe how we plan on transferring the results into modules for Resilipipe.

¹⁹ The dataset is available on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/10802427>.

²⁰ The service we used is <https://www.keyword-tools.org/en/>.

²¹ Refer to <https://touche.webis.de/clef25/touche25-web/advertisement-detection.html> for the task description.

We created the first comprehensive taxonomy of trigger warnings and the Webis Trigger Warning Corpus 2022, a dataset of 1 million fanfiction works from the platform Archive of Our Own (AO3).²² The authors that publish on AO3 assign a range of free-form tags to their works to inform readers about the content and communicate warnings. Building on the tag relations created by volunteer community experts, we semi-automatically mapped 41 million of these free-form tags into our taxonomy. This allows us to study how the AO3 community applies warnings to pieces of text and train models on the task of detecting potentially distressing content in natural language.

Figure 2: Taxonomy of Trigger Warnings

baseline. For different forms of Abuse (*Emotional, Physical, and Sexual Abuse*), we already found this to be the case and plan on extending the method to additional warnings. Building on this method, we can derive lexical indicators for the presence of potentially distressing content. These indicators can be used for both an efficient assignment of trigger warnings to pieces of texts as well as to collect passages for annotation to train more sophisticated models such as LLMs.

Based on the experience we gained while running the current setup of Resilipipe, we expect to create two modules for automated trigger warning assignment. The first module will be designed to be more light-weight and thus suitable to be run on all web pages of the daily crawls. It will likely take a dictionary-based approach by scanning the plain text of a web page for lexical indicators of a warning. The second module will emphasize quality over efficiency by applying a language model to the task. Given the resource demand and time complexity of language models, the second module will only be applied to a subset of all web pages. How this subset will be defined, is a topic of future

In a first study, we conducted an annotation experiment with 4,135 passages from works tagged for different forms of *Aggression (Violence, Death, War, and Abduction)* and *Discrimination (Racism, Homophobia, Misogyny, and Ableism)*.²³ For each passage, a set of three annotators was asked to decide if it required a warning for the form of *Aggression* or *Discrimination* that the containing work was tagged for. The experiments revealed the subjectivity of trigger warning assignment as the pairwise agreements between annotators showed only a “fair agreement” of 0.31-0.44 Cohen’s Kappa.

In ongoing research, we apply measures from corpus linguistics to test if works tagged for a given warning contain vocabulary expected for that warning significantly more often than a comparable

²² Matti Wiegmann, Magdalena Wolska, Christopher Schröder, Ole Borchart, Benno Stein, & Martin Potthast (2023). [Trigger Warning Assignment as a Multi-Label Document Classification Problem](#). In 61th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (ACL 2023).

²³ Matti Wiegmann, Jennifer Rakete, Magdalena Wolska, Benno Stein, & Martin Potthast (2024). [If there's a Trigger Warning, then where's the Trigger? Investigating Trigger Warnings at the Passage Level](#).

research. Potential avenues are web pages from highly frequented domains or pages that meet quality criteria with regards to their text.

4. Embeddings and Language Models for Multilingual RAG-based Systems

In recent years, advancements in Artificial Intelligence and Natural Language Processing have brought Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) systems to the forefront of Information Retrieval (IR) research. These systems have demonstrated considerable potential in enhancing Language Models by incorporating external knowledge, so-called Retrieval-Augmented Language Models (RALM), making them increasingly impactful across various applications. As this field continues to grow, we foresee an expanding role for RAG systems, particularly in multilingual contexts.

Our work aims to contribute to this progress, with a special focus on supporting European efforts in the development of multilingual RAG-based applications. To achieve this, we are committed to providing recent web data that is valuable for RAG systems. Specifically, we prepare and segment relevant web documents, offering them in both textual and vectorized forms, so that third parties can directly utilize the resulting corpus. This approach is designed to assist those who may find the computational demands of iteratively computing embeddings of recent web corpora too challenging.

To facilitate these efforts, we plan to deliver text embeddings alongside the web documents through the Open Web Index (OWI). The corresponding embedding datasets, called OWIE (Open Web Index Embeddings), will be made available on openwebindex.eu as well. Our research guides us in developing the OWIE service. Specifically, our research has focused on

- (1) selecting the right embedding models,
- (2) evaluating how boilerplate code²⁴ commonly present in web data affects retrieval performance, and
- (3) exploring the potential of agentic RAG.

With this initiative, we aim to support multilingual RAG systems and foster European digital innovation.

4.1 Identification of Families of Embedding Models

In the first part of our research, we explore the selection of embedding models to be used in RAG systems.²⁵ One of our focus points is the evaluation of similarities between models across various prominent families, including e5, t5, bge, and gte, as well as proprietary models from OpenAI and Cohere. We utilized multiple metrics to assess model similarity: Centered Kernel Alignment (CKA) to measure representational similarity, and Jaccard and rank similarity to evaluate retrieval performance in a RAG context. Our findings reveal distinct intra-family clusters, but also some inter-family similarities, particularly among the bge, UAE, and mxbai models. Each metric provided unique insights, with none being universally superior, highlighting the complexity of model selection. In our future work, we want to concentrate on evaluating model performance on large, real-world datasets and explore the impact of different text chunking strategies on embedding similarity. Besides that, we would like to incorporate additional similarity measures, which could enhance our understanding of factors influencing model similarity.

²⁴ One example for boilerplate code is the content of navigation bars or footers.

²⁵ Laura Caspari, Kanishka Ghosh Dastidar, Saber Zerhoubi, Jelena Mitrovic, & Michael Granitzer. (2024). [Beyond Benchmarks: Evaluating Embedding Model Similarity for Retrieval Augmented Generation Systems.](#)

4.2 Comparison of Chunking Methods

A major quality bottleneck regarding web texts compared to, e.g., academic datasets in the context of RAG is the heterogeneity in text length and structure. Most text embedding models of reasonable size and usable in web-scale settings limit their input to a context length shorter than the typical length of web documents. Hence, the raw text documents must be chunked, such that several meaningful vector representations correspond to a single web document. Furthermore, academic datasets commonly used for evaluating RAG systems contain properly cleaned and often short texts that answer a specific question. In contrast, web documents might contain long texts covering multiple topics and providing answers to a variety of questions. They also contain repetitive and uninformative content like navigation bars or footers. Such boilerplate text might impact retrieval performance negatively, if parts of it end up in the same chunk relevant text passages. In our work, we evaluate how retrieval performance is affected by boilerplate text and what chunking strategies promise good performance on web data.

4.3 Personalized and Agentic RAG

As part of our research, we developed PersonaRAG, a novel framework that integrates personalized, agent-based systems into Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) models.²⁶ Due to its agentic nature, it can significantly improve the relevance and accuracy of language model outputs considering personal preferences that are explicitly or implicitly available to the system. Unlike traditional RAG systems, PersonaRAG incorporates user-centric agents that dynamically adapt to user profiles, live session behaviors, and feedback. This personalized, agentic approach enables more precise content generation by continuously refining the interaction between users and the retrieval process. Experimental results demonstrate that PersonaRAG outperforms baseline models, achieving up to a 10% improvement in accuracy on various datasets. Despite its success, PersonaRAG's reliance on multiple API calls introduces potential latency and cost concerns. Future work will focus on optimizing these processes to enhance efficiency while maintaining the system's ability to deliver personalized, context-aware information. Further development will also explore additional user-centric agents to capture diverse user styles and preferences, broadening the applicability of the PersonaRAG system in information retrieval tasks.

²⁶ Saber Zerhoudi, & Michael Granitzer. (2024). [PersonaRAG: Enhancing Retrieval-Augmented Generation Systems with User-Centric Agents](#).

5. Conclusion and Outlook

This report provides a summary of different content analysis modules that are used to enrich the OpenWebIndex (OWI) with relevant metadata. The developed preprocessing pipeline Resilipipe, based on the web content extraction library Resiliparse, provides modules for processing and analyzing web crawls and can be extended as required by thirdparties.

We provide general information about web pages that can be directly extracted from the WARC and HTTP headers of a document. Other modules assign genre labels based on either the domain of a web page or its content. Collection indices, that can be used for the division of the index into subsets, are directly created in the OWI-generation pipeline and can also be further extended.

The analysis of the web page content itself includes the extraction and labelling of geographic information. Further, we develop approaches for distinguishing between human-written and LLM-generated web content. Another aspect is to implement a suitable approach for the summarization of arguments in a document.

In the context of computational ethics, we are concerned with the question of how we can deal with misleading or disturbing web content. A first approach for the detection of advertisements woven directly into the responses of conversational search engines is presented. Furthermore, we investigate the assignment of trigger warnings for potentially harmful web content, so that users can make informed decisions about which search results they want to view.

In order to support retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) systems in general, and multilingual RAG-based systems in particular, we plan to provide web documents as embeddings alongside the OWI for direct usage. A framework for the integration of personal information into agent-based RAG systems is developed to generate more relevant content for a user.

For the second half of the project, we plan to deepen our research on the detection of LLM-generated content, the analysis of arguments including temporal analysis, the detection and blocking of LLM-generated advertising in conversational search systems, and the creation of embeddings for web documents. Further, we continue the integration and evaluation of LLM-generated geographic annotations for the training of models for the extraction of geographic information from web documents.

6. Appendix

6.1 List of Acronyms

Acronym or Abbreviation	Term
DEM	Demonstrator
DG Connect	European Commission Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology
HORIZON-RIA	Horizon - Research and Innovation Action
HPC	High-Performance Computing
NER	Name Entity Recognition
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OWI	Open Web Index
OWS or OWS.eu	OpenWebSearch.eu project
RIA	Research and Innovations Action
SERP	Search Engine Result Page